

“Awareness about Major Changes in the Consumer Protection Bill, 2018”

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Abstract

To overcome from certain limitations existed in the present Consumer Protection Act the Central Government has planned to make necessary changes in the Act to protect the rights and interests of the consumers. Hence, the Consumer Protection Bill, 2018 was passed in the Lok Sabha to replace the existing Consumer Protection Act, 1986. But it will come into existence only after it gets approval from the Rajya Sabha. The present paper is prepared to create awareness about major changes in the Consumer Protection Bill, 2018.

Keywords: The Consumer Protection Bill, 2018 includes: setting up of Central Consumers Protection Authority (CCPA), setting up of Mediation Cell in each consumer court, increased the monetary jurisdiction and widens the territorial jurisdiction, introduces the concept of product liability, introduces punishment for misleading advertisement.

Introduction

Worldwide consumer movement was started during the 20th century to protect consumer's interests. The prominent countries in which the consumer movement was started are: USA, England, Japan, Germany, Malaysia, Australia, and South Africa. In India also the consumer movement was started by various voluntary consumer organizations in the 20th century. Now a day the VCO's are also playing an important role to create awareness about the Consumer Protection Act by organizing seminars, workshops, road shows, etc. in different areas.

Consumer Protection Act, 1986

For the success of consumer movements and to protect the interests of the consumers in India, the Government has enacted the special Law for consumers called “The Consumer Protection Act, 1986”. The Act provides certain provisions for the establishment of Consumer Courts at various levels such as District Forum, State Commission and National Commission for the settlement of consumers' disputes. The Consumer Protection Act, 1986 came into existence from 24th December 1986. Hence, every year 24th December is celebrated as “National Consumers Day” to remember the milestone of the Act by organizing various programmes on Consumerism, creating awareness about their rights and duties so that no consumer will be exploited by business community. The present Consumer Protection Act, 1986 has been amended three times since its enactment i.e. in 1991, in 1993 and

in 2002. But still there are certain limitations are existed as remained unchanged. In the Globalized economy, there is a lot of changes occurred in the business activities like online marketing, online banking, online services, etc. have created new options and opportunities to mislead the consumers by way of unfair trade practices and unethical business practices. This influenced to change certain clauses in the Consumer Protection Act in the interest of the consumers in India. In view of this, the Central Government has appointed the Standing Committee of Parliament under the Chairmanship of J.C. Divakar Reddy. On the basis of recommendations of the Standing Committee, the Consumer Protection Bill, 2018 was introduced in the Parliament on 05-01- 2018, which was passed in the Lok Sabha on the last day of the Parliament Session i.e. on December 20th 2018 to replace the existing Consumer Protection Act, 1986. But the Bill is lying in the Rajya Sabha to get its approval. It will become an Act only after getting approval from the Rajya Sabha.

Major Highlights of the Consumer Protection Bill, 2018

The contents of the Consumer Protection Bill, 2018 are really beneficial to the consumers. Hence majority of the Voluntary Consumer Organizations and general public have supported the proposed Bill. Some of the major changes in the Bill are highlighted in this paper.

1. **Central Consumer Protection Authority:** The Consumer Protection Bill 2018 provides for establishment of a Regulatory Body called as the Central Consumer Protection Authority, which will be an executive agency to regulate matters relating to violation of rights of consumers, unfair trade practices and false or misleading advertisements, which are against the interests of consumers. Any person can send a complaint to the Central Consumer Protection Authority relating to violation of consumer rights or unfair trade practices or misleading advertisements.

If the complaint is satisfied by the Central Consumer Protection Authority, it may pass an order to recall the goods or withdrawal of services which are dangerous, hazardous or unsafe, or for reimbursement of the prices to the consumers and discontinuation of such practices which are unfair and against the consumers' interest.

2. **Product Liability:** A new chapter has been introduced in the Bill to enforce product liability against manufacturers and even make them to recall the product from entire market if any product or service is harmful to a consumer by such defective product manufactured or sold. A product liability action may be brought by a complainant against a product manufacturer or a product service provider or a product seller, as the case may be, for any harm caused to him on account of a defective product or deficiency in services.
3. **Unfair Contracts:** The Bill identifies six types of unfair contracts, including contracts: requiring excessive security deposits; or imposing any disproportionate penalty on the consumer, for the breach of contract; or refusing to accept early repayment of debts on payment of applicable penalty; or entitling a party to the contract to terminate such contract unilaterally, without reasonable cause.. Any complaint against unfair contracts can be filed with the State Commission or the National Commission.
4. **Unfair Trade Practices:** Three more types of unfair trade practices are added to the existing list of unfair trade practices. They are as follows:
 - a. Not issuing bill or receipt for the goods sold or services rendered.
 - b. Refusing to take back or withdraw defective goods or services within stipulated period as mentioned in the bill or within a period of thirty days; and
 - c. Disclosing of personal information to other person without taking consent from the consumer.
5. **Establishment of Mediation Centers in Consumer Courts:** The Bill provides special provisions for setting up of Mediation Centers as an Alternative Dispute Redressal Mechanism in

Consumer Courts. If any party wishes to settle their complaint out of the court then the District Forum or State or the National Commission may inform the parties to give a written consent stating that they will settle their dispute through Mediation Centers.

6. Introduction of E-Commerce: In the present Act there is no provision as regards to purchases made through e-commerce. However, the proposed Bill covers the buying or selling of goods or services including digital products over digital or electronic network, which will be beneficial to the young people who always likes to purchase digitally.
7. Enhancement of the Pecuniary Jurisdiction: Looking into the current market trends and decrease in the money value, the Bill proposes to increase the pecuniary jurisdiction of the Consumer Disputes Redressal Agencies as given below.

The Pecuniary Jurisdiction of District Forum increased from Rs. 20 Lakhs to Rs. 1 Crore.

The Pecuniary Jurisdiction of State Commission increased from Rs. 1 Crore to 10 Crore.

The Pecuniary Jurisdiction of the National Commission will be for more than Rs.10 Crore.

8. Territorial Jurisdiction: The Bill has made changes to the Territorial Jurisdiction of the Consumer Disputes Redressal Agencies also. It includes the place of residence or business of the complainant, in addition to the opposite party place of occurrence of the cause of action.
9. Imprisonment for False and Misleading Advertisements, Sale of Spurious Products and Adulterated Food:

Section 89 of the Bill states that there will be two years of imprisonment and a fine of Rs. 10 Lakhs or both for misleading Advertisements.

Section 90 of the Bill states that imprisonment for sale of adulterated food,

While Section 91 provides for imprisonment for sale of spurious goods

Conclusion

The Consumer Protection Bill, 2018 has introduced many provisions as stated above to protect and safeguard the interest of the consumers in India and to keep up with the emerging market trends and further aims to simplify the consumer dispute redressal process by including provisions for electronic filing and provisions for hearing or examination through video conferencing. Once it is passed in the Rajy Sabha, the Bill will certainly be a step forward towards protecting the rights and interests of consumers in India.

I conclude the paper by quoting

“Consumer is always king”.....